

FREQUENCY OF OCCURRENCE AND RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICINAL POISONS IN CHILDREN IN THE SAMARKAND REGION

Musoyev Sodiqjon Toirovich

Assistant of the Department of Clinical pharmacology
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The analysis of the latest literary data shows that every year the specific weight of the children of this pathology is increasing and there is no tendency to reduce. The progressive growth of this pathology. The world-based register increases due to the fact that the pharmaceutical industry is produced annually, more than drugs, which are widely used in practical health care and in particular in pediatrics. Polypharmacy, self-heating, irrational use of antibiotics and other medicines can lead to medicinal poisoning. In this paper we studied the frequency of occurrence, risk factors for the development of medicinal poems according to the Samarkand region.*

Keywords: *medications, poisoning, children.*

Sharp poisoning in children is urgent state of requiring emergency medical care. One, the parties are determined by the suddenness of the disease, with another rapid growth of intoxication of powers in vain due to anatomy-physiological characteristics of the childhood that can lead to tragic outcome (1,2,3).

The growth of the situation of patients and children for intimate, high lethality served as the reasons for the full study of this pathology by scientists.

In the periodic literature, sufficiently published works devoted to acute poisoning in children.

Poisoning (intimacy) acute or chronic threatening life state developing due to interaction of the human body and poison. Poisoning can develop as a result of receipt from environment (exogenous poisons), as well as a result of saturation of the body toxins in violation of the function of organs and systems (endogenous poisons). Poison is an ethnicity that is imposed on the human ordinary personnel, including human deep, or a different derivation of biochemical, physiological, genetic, mental and other processes and functions notes the Baranov AA.

In developed countries, the number of deaths from acute poisoning in children significantly exceeds the number of lethal outcomes from many infectious diseases together (3,5,6).

In the world, the situation of acute poisoning is steadily growing. In connection with the wide spread in the environment of various chemical and pharmacological preparations. More and more children are in the toxicological departments with a diagnosis of acute poisoning (4,6).

Purpose of the study- to study the frequency of occurrence of medicinal poisoning in children and determine the risk factors that promote the development of medicinal poems in children.

Materials and methods of research.

The results of the analysis of 324 cases of acute poisoning of hospitalized intense pediatrics and the department of children's resuscitation of the RNCSEMP SP were hospitalized in the two branches of the acute poisoning. For periods 2020-2021-2022. From the spotted poisoning, patients with medicine poisoning. When analyzing the history of diseases, focus on the frequency of occurrence on a thorough collection of anamnesis, age, sex, residence, residence seasons, structure of poisoning and risk factors. The age of the children was from 0 to 14 years. Girls were -173, boys -151.

The results of the study

Not organized children and adolescents that do not attend the children's gardens, nasal, do not learn, do not work and constitute the majority of hospitalized sharp medicinal poisoning-188 children, which was 58.02%. Организованные Children were 136 children and amounted to 41.97%.

Not without interest was analyzed at what time of the day the patients received a hospital. We are stated that the greatest amount of income was in the range of 12:00 to 24:00 (75%). The most significant 20:00 to 24:00 (39%) less than hospitalization has occurred from 4:00 to 8:00. The results of our patients under study hospitalization depending on the season of the year confirmed the regularity of the seasonal distribution of hospitalization with drug poisoning (Table 2), the maximum of hospitalization was in winter 98-30.24%, then in spring 86-26.54% and in the fall of 78-24.07% and the low-hospitalization was accidentally 62-19.13%.

Analyzing seasonal fluctuations in poisoning, revealed that they are often children with medicinal poisoning in the cold season, which is due to the frequency of colds, thereby increasing the use of medicines and the aircraft of parent. Also important is the fact that children in winter have more time at home.

Sweet taste of syrups, vitamins with a beautiful tall, desire to imitate adults they play in the doctor and sick, which can lead to porcelain outcome. During the cold and cold acidity, the parents of children give the shock doses of ascorbic acid, supplementing double doses of vitamins. The frequency of occurrence of medicinal poisoning in children depending on the place of residence (Table 3) showed that the patient of the sick of 188.66 patients living in the city of 181 patients in 414.13% residents were used to the hospitalization of children from the village at the place of residence in the branches.

Analysis of hospitalized patients, depending on the severity of the state (Table 4) of children and adolescents, showed that 74 patients (22.83%) had a light degree of poisoning, in the state of medium severity, 187 patients hospitalized (57.71%) and children. The defendants who have been in the department were severely pulled amounted to 63 patients (19.44%).

It should be pointed out, children with a heavy degree of poison were hospitalized in a children's reanimarial department.

An important significance in the development of medicinal poems in children has risk factors that affect the formation of medicinal poisoning in children (Table 5).

Along with the usual methods of research, we considered it necessary to identify risk factors and interpret the obtained data, in particular, to bear patients and healthy on the group of patients and healthy on their exposure to the complex of factors and mathematical methods to determine the differences between the groups of patients and healthy. Therefore, one of the important tasks in the prevention of the growth of medicinal poems in children is the definition of

the children's population with increased risk of poisoning. This will contribute to the successful reduction in poisoning in children.

Based on the obtained data we have been conditionally highlighted among children three groups of risk of disease

IA group of low (unlikely risk) in the addition of diagnostic coefficients will be equal to 4, 50 and below

Ii The group - average (probable) risk when the diagnostic coefficient is additionally equal to - 4, 50 up to + 450

Iii A group of high (inevitable) risk when the diagnostic coefficient is frequent equal to +4, 50 and higher

The work was shown that DC (+2,27) was high in young children, which is due to the insurance of adults. Children at this age independently use medicines, taking them for candy, becoming interested in their original packaging, beautiful look and sweet taste. In children who often have colds with disease (often a child's child). The DC was equal to +2.62, which is associated with frequent use of medicines. Allergic diseases also require the frequent use of DC + 1,362 medications. A similar situation is noted in patients' parents (DK +1,765) and grandparents (DK + 1,818). DK also turned out to be high when parents, grandparents take their medicines in the presence of children (DK +2,314). The work was also shown, more often children with medicinal poison are hospitalized in the cold season (DK + 1,43) that is also associated with the frequency of colds.

Conclusions. Thus, children having significant risk factors: early age, often a sick child, children or parents have allergic diseases, the cold period of the year should be under the close attention of prefabricated pediatrics in order to have timely preventing activities that can contribute to a decrease in the number of children with medicinal poisoning.

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